

BioINSouth

Supporting regional environmental sustainability assessment for the BIO-based sectors to improve INnovation, INdustries and INclusivity in SOUTH Europe

Deliverable 3.3 HUB Action Plan

Cyprus

Czech Republic

France

Greece

Portugal

Italy

Slovenia

Spain

Türkyie

BioINSouth

Supporting regional environmental sustainability assessment for the BIO-based sectors to improve INnovation, INdustries and INclusivity in SOUTH Europe

Project title	Supporting regional environmental sustainability assessment for the bio-based sectors to improve innovation, industries and inclusivity in South Europe
Project acronym	BioINSouth
Grant agreement ID	101156363
Project start date	01/06/2024
Duration	36 months

D3.3 HUB Action Plan

Due date	31/08/2025
Delivery date	29/08/2025
Work Package	WP3
Author(s) responsible	Marie Kubáňková, George Sakellaris, Aikaterini Panailidou
Contributor(s)	Pierluigi Argoneto, Lara Carlet, María García Alegre, Marina Barquero León, Filipa Sacadura, Carlos Silva, Konstantinos Vorgias, Cristina Viera, Alenka Dovč, Eva Mametz, Evi Demetriou
Reviewer(s)	Andrea Cavallaro (INNEN), Nadia Vougiannopoulou (PNO) Pierluigi Argoneto, Lara Carlet (SPRING)
Version	Final
Dissemination level	PU- Public

[VERSION AND AMENDMENT HISTORY]

Version	Date (DD/MM/YYYY)	Created by/ Amended by	Review of changes
V0.1	05/08/2025	Marie Kubáňková, Aikaterini Panailidou	First draft of the deliverable
V1	13/08/2025	Marie Kubáňková, Aikaterini Panailidou	Action Plans included in the document
V1.1	18/08/2025	Andrea Cavallaro (INNEN)	Peer Review
V1.1.1	19/08/2025	Nadia Vougogiannopoulou	Peer Review
V2	26/08/2025	Aikaterini Panailidou	Comments incorporated
Final	29/08/2025	Pierluigi Argoneto, Lara Carlet (SPRING)	Final version ready for coordinator review and submission

Contents

Executive Summary.....	5
1 Introduction.....	6
2 Methodology	7
3 Template for the BioINSouth HUB Action Plan	8
4 Conclusions.....	10
4.1 Horizontal Conclusions from the Action Plans.....	10
4.2 Vertical conclusions from each BioINSouth HUB Action Plan.....	10
Annex 1: Action Plan of the BioINSouth HUB of Andalusia.....	13
Annex 2: Action Plan of the BioINSouth HUB of Asturias	25
Annex 3: Action Plan of the BioINSouth HUB of Campania	33
Annex 3: Action Plan of the BioINSouth HUB of Centro Region	44
Annex 5: Action Plan of the BioINSouth HUB of Cyprus.....	52
Annex 6: Action Plan of the BioINSouth HUB of Nouvelle- Aquitaine.....	65
Annex 7: Action Plan of the BioINSouth HUB of the Peloponnese.....	72
Annex 8: Action Plan of the BioINSouth HUB of Slovenia.....	92

Abbreviations	
D	Deliverable
DoA	Description of Action
KoM	Kick-Off Meeting
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
M	Month
MARG	Multi- Actor Regional Groups
MoU	Memorandum of Understanding
NGO	Non Governmental Organisation
QH	Quadruple Helix
R&I	Research and Innovation
SME	Small- Medium Enterprise
ToR	Terms of Reference
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

The Deliverable D3.3 *HUB Action Plan* presents the **Action Plans developed by the BioINSouth HUB Coordinators**, offering a clear roadmap for collaborative actions that will strengthen the regional bioeconomy through inclusive, goal-oriented and stakeholder-driven initiatives.

Each BioINSouth HUB has developed its own Action Plan through a **co-creative process** involving active engagement with stakeholders identified and clustered in Work Package 2 (WP2), ensuring their full participation and commitment. These Action Plans reflect the **identified needs of stakeholders**, articulate a **shared vision** and define **specific tasks and responsibilities** necessary to achieve the common goals of the HUBs.

To facilitate a structured and harmonised approach, it has been prepared a comprehensive Action Plan template, which is provided in *Section 3* of this document, strictly connected to what has been described in the previous D3.1 and D3.2. This template has served as a framework for all HUB Coordinators, enabling them to formulate context-specific Action Plans while ensuring consistency across the initiative and the project timeline.

The Action Plans of the BioINSouth HUBs will serve as the basis for the HUB activities until (and after) the completion of the project and especially in the implementation phase (Task 3.3) as well as support the BioINSouth Network (Task 3.2). Moreover, the Action Plan template could be considered as a good starting point in case of replication of the same, or equivalent, initiative in other regions not originally comprised in the 8 ones described in the project.

1 Introduction

The Action Plan of each BioINSouth HUB is the main output of Task 3.3 and it was prepared by the corresponding BioINSouth Coordinators benefiting from the outcomes from WP2, WP4 and the other tasks in WP3. The official Kick-off Meetings (KoMs) of the BioINSouth HUBs co-incident with the second co-creation workshop envisaged in the BioINSouth Project activities. During each KOMs, the BioINSouth Coordinators engaged with members of their BioINSouth HUBs presenting not only the vision of their BioINSouth HUB but also the draft Action Plan of the HUB they were preparing at the time. During the co-creation part of the KoMs, the HUB Coordinators had the opportunity to receive feedback and discuss with the HUB Members on the details of the Action Plans and the foreseen activities. The meetings took place from late June 2025 throughout the month of July 2025, with this deliverable being the summarisation of these experiences and resulting Action Plans.

In line with the preparation of the individual BioINSouth Action Plans, the BioINSouth HUB coordinators were given the opportunity to also research the [national and regional bioeconomy related policies](#) that are in effect in their regions or the absence of them, giving them a unique and holistic detailed understanding of the bioeconomy status in their region of activity.

This document is structured as follows:

- **Section 1** consists of the introduction.
- **Section 2** briefly presents the **methodology** applied to prepare the Action Plans.
- **Section 3** summarises the **Action Plans**, highlighting **key challenges** and **reflections** collected from the HUB coordinators during the validation process.
- **Section 4** presents the **full Action Plans** elaborated by the BioINSouth HUB Coordinators.

The document is therefore providing a **comprehensive overview of the co-created Action Plans**, serving as a foundation for coordinated efforts to advance bioeconomy innovation in the BioINSouth regions.

2 Methodology

Following the establishment of the BioINSouth HUBs on month M12 of the Project and the Co-Creation Workshop, the methodology of perceiving and developing an Action Plan for a bioeconomy HUB was promptly made available to the BioINSouth HUB Coordinators through D3.2 “HUB guidelines Final”. In the deliverable’s annexes the HUB Coordinators could find all the necessary instructions on developing a HUB Action Plan and on organising a Workshop for the members of a bioeconomy HUB.

The development of the Action Plans was the sole responsibility of the BioINSouth HUB Coordinators, since they are the most knowledgeable party capable of putting together all the necessary information needed by the HUB Members and other stakeholders to fully understand and effectively communicate the importance of the work to be carried out by the BioINSouth HUBs. Preliminary work on this front was made during the WP2 activities on the Multi- Actor Regional Groups (MARG) establishment as well as WP3 activities on establishing the BioINSouth HUBs (Milestone 2) and stakeholder engagement. Some section of the Action Plans -particularly those concerning the activity plan and the sustainability of the HUB - were validated with the HUB Members through the co-creation workshops. The specific contents of the HUB Action Plans to be discussed and validated, as well as the extent of this validation, were determined at the discretion of the HUB Coordinator, based and their knowledge of the HUB Members and their expertise.

The BioINSouth HUB Coordinators were provided with a template of the HUB Action Plans they were invited to develop. The template is referenced in this deliverable under *Section 3*. The nature of the template was flexible enough to account for the differences in the maturity level of the bioeconomy situation and relevant stakeholders in each region. This to support the HUB Coordinators in developing and/or modifying a specific HUB Action Plan fitting to their regions’ specificities and needs serving both their HUBs’ identities and the better communication with their HUB Members and stakeholders.

BIOEAST HUB CR communicated and provided feedback to the HUB Coordinators for the Action Plans or the Kick-off Meetings’ organisation upon request and provided comments and guidance for the completion of the Action Plans.

The individual Action Plans were examined particularly from these aspects:

1. Stakeholder Landscape & Engagement

- Types of stakeholders involved (e.g., academia, Small-Medium Enterprises (SMEs), large industries, policymakers, Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs)).
- Stakeholder needs and expectations gathered during co-creation.

2. Barriers, Challenges and Needs

- Barriers and challenges identified (e.g., regulatory, financial, knowledge gaps).
- Human, financial and technical resources identified as crucial.

The reason for looking closely at point 1) is obvious: it’s always interesting to compare stakeholder structures and see how much- if at all- they differ between regions. **This comparison could theoretically help BioINSouth HUB Coordinators learn from each other**, especially when it comes to attracting specific stakeholder groups – be it policymakers, industry players, or academic partners – that one HUB has managed to engage while another hasn’t. The rationale behind point 2) might not be as immediately evident. Newly established BioINSouth HUBs inevitably encounter numerous challenges, which place significant demands on their Coordinators. By identifying challenges that are common across HUBs, shared ground – lessons learnt or best practices - can emerge, potentially inspiring the BioINSouth Initiative, which is being developed as a genuine bottom-up effort.

3 Template for the BioINSouth HUB Action Plan

The following template was prepared to assist the BioINSouth HUB Coordinators in creating their BioINSouth HUB Action Plans. The template served as a guide for the HUB Coordinators, who were encouraged to take initiative in including any additional information they deemed necessary. Included in the Annexes of this document are the individual Action Plans of each HUB, in alphabetical order. The Action Plans of all BioINSouth HUBs will be also utilised for the needs of each HUB and in communication with the HUB Members.

Introduction

General information on the region, short description of its position, climate, population, area, mentions of any notable positions or roles in the economy and any specifics in regional governance. Short description of the BioINSouth HUB Coordinating organisation and their role in the region, their expertise, this obligation to establish and run a BioINSouth HUB in the region under the BioINSouth Project and Initiative.

Goals and Objectives

Establish SMART goals for the HUB (Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, Time-bound) that align with the project KPIs and regional bioeconomy opportunities (see D3.1 and D3.2). Translate goals into actionable and measurable tasks that can be implemented at the HUB level.

Include the Vision and Mission of the BioINSouth HUB and the general added value of the HUB to the regional dynamic.

Target Audience

Overview of the governance status, the features of stakeholders engaged as MARG members and Participants, in relation to the niches present to the region and their desired contribution to the activities of the BioINSouth HUB.

Stakeholder Group	All Institutions that have been mapped so far and their potential key role to the BioINSouth HUB	Ideas for outreach activities	Specific needs from the BioINSouth Project or Initiative with regards to the cooperation with this stakeholder group

Situation Analysis

Policy and governmental strategies that are in play for the bioeconomy sector of the regions. Political background and way of operation that could wither help or hinder the work of the HUB and the support of bioeconomy advancement in the region.

Value chains of special interest either due to their existing growth or potential in the region.

What is identified as the biggest barrier in the development of bioeconomy in the region and any other aspects that will need to be paid special attention to.

Strategy Development

Set realistic deadlines and progress indicators, considering interdependencies and flexibility to adapt as needed.

Added value for key stakeholder groups based on the situational and stakeholder analysis.

Implementation Plan of Activities

Translate goals into actionable and measurable tasks that can be implemented at the HUB level. Clearly designate roles and task ownership across the HUB team and its stakeholder partners to foster accountability. Try to be general and flexible in your descriptions, when possible, to allow yourself the ability to adapt to emergent situations. Also possible for you to focus on the identified topics of interest for the BioINSouth HUB (if any at this point).

See also D3.2 and keep in mind the project requirements.

Resource Allocation

Determine the financial, human and technical resources necessary to implement the plan, leveraging project tools and external inputs where appropriate.

Monitoring and Evaluation

Build in regular tracking, feedback loops and performance assessment mechanisms to ensure continuous improvement and alignment with stakeholder expectations.

Risk Assessment and Mitigation

Clearly designate roles and task ownership across the HUB team and its stakeholder partners to foster accountability.

Communication Plan

What you believe is the best course of action in communicating with your Members such as means, topics, duration, frequency, etc. Any main points that need to be communicated every time, or progress updates you may want to share regularly with your Members.

Long Term Sustainability Strategy

Description of any long-term plans that you would like the BioINSouth HUB to involved in or aim towards. Present the identified possibilities in your specific case on additional support of the BioINSouth HUB in terms of funding and advancement of your work after the completion of the BioINSouth Project and working under the upcoming BioINSouth Initiative.

4 Conclusions

4.1 Horizontal conclusions from the Action Plans

The BioINSouth HUBs have prepared their HUB Action Plans by considering the multitude of factors that can affect the work of the HUB and the bioeconomy advancement of the region. In terms of stakeholders, the quadruple helix approach promoted by the Project Objectives is evident in all HUBs, with some opting to categorise their stakeholders mainly in these four groups of policy makers, academia, industry and civil society. Some choosing to detail the classification of their stakeholders adding groups like SMEs, NGOs and others. This, of course, is greatly dependent on the status of the stakeholder mapping and engagement in each HUB and the willingness of these stakeholders to engage in conversation with the HUBs. Noteworthy is the observation that usually the SMEs choose to operate in silo and are not easily reachable for intensive collaboration.

All HUB Coordinators are emphasising through their Action Plans the importance of an extensive and intensive analysis of the regional regulatory framework and gathering all relevant administrative information, not only to better grasp the regional situation but to also have an advantage in engaging with policy makers and administrative representatives of their region. Furthermore, all have identified the barriers of administrative inconsistencies and loss of interest both by the HUB Members as well as the regional stakeholders, with some also considering the high effect of environmental factors in the HUB's and the region's activities. While some HUBs are for now focusing more on the regional stakeholders, some have taken the step to also engage with additional stakeholders outside the region, heavily influenced by the level of maturity and knowledge of bioeconomy in each region. Even with some commonalities between the key areas of the bioeconomy sector in some cases, there is a varied pool of bioeconomy opportunities that are open for the BioINSouth HUBs to explore and cooperate with each other in exploiting, with the fragmentation of the regional value chains being one of the leading problems identified by most in terms of biomass valorisation.

The BioINSouth HUB Action Plans reflect the operative situation of each HUB and sometimes differ in the detailing of some activities and working aspects of the HUBs due to the very different regional situations the BioINSouth HUB Coordinators are called to face. Even so, all of them have planned carefully and to the extent they are allowed, the core of their BioINSouth HUBs.

4.2 Vertical conclusions from each BioINSouth HUB Action Plan

ANDALUSIA

The **BioINSouth HUB of Andalusia** is active in a region that is one of the leading forces of bioeconomy in the EU, with regional strategies in place that serve as a reference for other regions. One of the main concerns of the HUB will be the maximisation of resource efficiency while also reducing the environmental impact. Among others, the main challenges identified lie in the scalability and standardisation of procedures, as well as the lack of flexibility on available financing instruments. The identified stakeholders represent the pillars of the region and will both benefit and support the HUB in networking and communication, utilisation of regional assets, educational needs identification and social awareness, with the HUB monitoring and addressing any lack of interest and low engagement from the HUB Members and stakeholders.

ASTURIAS

Asturias' key bioeconomy sectors are agri-food, livestock, forestry and fisheries. In the **BioINSouth HUB of Asturias**, the stakeholders are brought together in a holistic network promoting bioeconomy innovations in the region for the long term. With numerous stakeholders being active in more than one sector, the main topics of activity are industry, academia, research and innovation, or policy. Even considering one identified regional bioeconomy policy strategy, bioeconomy and biomass valorisation especially are in the early stages and the HUB Members have identified the importance of the BioINSouth HUB to support the region with the promotion and organisation of such activities. Apart from the risk of low participation and resource sustainability, some of the main identified barriers for the HUB's activities will also be fragmented models of biomass valorisation, as well as regulatory barriers and uncertainties and a potential hesitancy to cooperate with HUB from both policy makers and civil society.

CAMPANIA

The Campania region is increasingly strengthening their bioeconomy related activities, which they have identified and a strategic driver for change and development in the region. The **BioINSouth HUB of Campania** will aim to promote dialogue on regional planning, support the exploration of pilot project opportunities, contribute to public awareness campaigns and increase student engagement with the help of their members. The main barrier in all of Italy is the lack of clear and supportive regulatory framework for bioeconomy advancement, especially on secondary raw materials and cascading use of biomass.

CENTRO REGION

The **BioINSouth HUB of Centro Region** has identified bioeconomy as the engine for sustainable growth in the region and beyond. The HUB will serve as an example of growth and connection to other EU initiatives that are great options for collaboration an inspiration. The identified stakeholders are derived from multiple fronts of the driving forces in the region and all members are actively contributing to enhancing the search. Great caution is given to the environmental challenges the region is facing, like susceptibility to forest fires, desertification and biodiversity loss, which is accompanied by big data gaps. This drives the HUB to identify a big opportunity in the exploration and support in digital solutions, getting support from additional funding and utilising resources from the member organisations.

CYPRUS

Cyprus is an island nation where bioeconomy is still in the early stages, meaning the focus will be heavily placed in education and awareness, which needs focused policy and investment support. Many stakeholders have been identified that follow the vision of the **BioINSouth HUB of Cyprus** with economic, social, academic and political interests. Careful consideration and special attention will be paid to the potential of a misalignment of the interests of the stakeholders to those of the BioINSouth HUB and the achievement of a strong foundation through regional activities and interest in the network, managing the priorities and expectations of the members and stakeholders.

NOUVELLE-AQUITAINE

The **BioINSouth HUB of Nouvelle-Aquitaine** is active in a region with strong agri-food, forestry, aerospace and renewable energy sectors. In terms of stakeholders, the region has a diverse bioeconomy ecosystem that brings together actors that can accelerate bioeconomy advancement, including supply and demand stakeholders. The difficulties in the HUB activities will be brought by the lack of political will and alignment of interests, as well as socio-economic and environmental factors. The definition of possible resources and their allocation will follow gaining concrete experience in cooperating with the HUB Members and external stakeholders and more detailed discussions in the possibilities.

PELOPONNESE

The **BioINSouth HUB of the Peloponnese** brings together an impressive number and variety of stakeholders, not only from the region but also at a national level, who want to be a part of PeloponNEXT and leverage the regional strengths in a drive for innovation. The main factors that need to be considered are, among others, the regulatory complexity and social acceptance, the frequent political turnover and changes in political priorities and especially the limited resources and infrastructure, as well as the significant environmental risks of the region. The detailed Action Plan, distribution of responsibilities and HUB resource allocation will support the crucial smooth operation for the Members and stakeholders.

SLOVENIA

The **BioINSouth HUB of Slovenia** can bring together actors from its region to align under not only the BioINSouth objectives but also in accordance with other European Initiatives as well. With a strong ministerial and regional chamber representation in the stakeholders, the BioINSouth HUB will operate as a coordination and knowledge exchange platform, connecting the stakeholders also with the BIOEAST Initiative and other EU projects. With a fragmented official ministerial and regulatory representation of bioeconomy and multiple barriers in implementation throughout the regional value chains, the effective transfer and uptake of bioeconomy innovations will need the structured support of the BioINSouth HUB, considering the long-term sustainability of not only the HUB but the Slovenian bioeconomy ser.

BioINSouth Info Box

The BioINSouth project aims to support decision-makers to incorporate considerations of ecological limits into their regional bioeconomy strategies and roadmaps relevant to circular bio-based activities. We aim to develop guidelines and digital tools, considering the safe and sustainable by design (SSbD) assessment framework, to support the adoption of innovative methodologies to assess environmental impacts in multiple industrial bio-based systems, increasing regional competitiveness and innovation capacity, and contributing to the EU fair & green transition.

Find out more:

Website: <https://www.bioinsouth.eu/>

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/104361906/>

YouTube: <https://www.youtube.com/@BioINSouth>

Contact coordinator:

SPRING the Italian Circular Bioeconomy Cluster info@clusterspring.it

© European Union, 2025. Reuse is authorised provided the source is acknowledged. BioINSouth project (Grant Agreement No. 101156363)

Authors: Marie Kubáňková, George Sakellaris, Aikaterini Panailidou (BIOEAST CR), Pierluigi Argonet, Lara Carlet (SPRING), María García Alegre, Marina Barquero León (CTA), Filipa Sacadura, Carlos Silva (P-BIO), Konstantinos Vorgias (NKUA), Cristina Viera (ASINCAR), Alenka Dovč (ACIS), Eva Mametz (ASOI), Evi Demetriou (FredU),

Review by: Andrea Cavallaro, Nadia Vougiannopoulou (PNO), Pierluigi Argoneto, Lara Carlet (SPRING)

This document was published as “D3.3 HUB Action Plan”, and as part of the project “BioINSouth: Supporting regional environmental sustainability assessment for the BIO-based sectors to improve INnovation, INdustries and INclusivity in SOUTH Europe” (Grant Agreement No. 101156363), co-funded by the European Union and supported by the Circular Bio-based Europe Joint Undertaking and its members. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CBE JU. Neither the European Union nor the CBE JU can be held responsible for them.

Reproduction is authorised provided the source is acknowledged.